

Regional Distance-based k-NN Classification

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Abstract: The k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) is very simple and powerful approach to conceptually approximate real-valued or discrete-valued target function. Many researchers have recently approved that K-NN is a high-prediction accuracy algorithm for a variety of real-world systems using many different types of datasets. However, as we know, k-NN is a type of lazy learning algorithms as it has to compare to each of stored training examples for each observed instance. Besides, the prediction accuracy of k-NN is under the influence of K values. Mostly, the higher K values make the algorithm yield lower prediction accuracy according to our experiments. For these issues, this paper focuses on two properties that are to upgrade the classification accuracy by introducing Regional Distance-based k-NN (RD-kNN) and to speed up the processing time performance of k-NN by applying multi-threading approach. For the experiments, we used the real data sets (wine, iris, heart stalog, breast cancer, and breast tissue) from UCI machine learning repository. According to our test cases and simulations carried out, it was also experimentally confirmed that the new approach, RD-kNN, has a better performance than classical kNN.

Keywords: k-NN, RD-kNN

I. INTRODUCTION

The k-Nearest Neighbor is one of the most simple and powerful classification methods in machine learning area. On the other hand, the k-NN is a semi-supervised learning algorithm that requires training data and a predefined k value to find the k^{th} nearest instance based on distance computations [1]. The primary task of k-NN is to classify an observed instance by assigning the training case, which has the most frequent class among the k nearest neighbors.

In Fig.1, the basic function of k-NN can be clearly seen. For $K=3$, in the inner most circle, the observed instance that is a plus symbol belongs to the blue circle according to voting system, whereas for $K=9$, the observed instance will be classified as a red triangle.

However, the difficult situation of voting system makes k-NN go into a terrible struggle in making a decision. Fig.2 points out the difficult situations of k-NN in classification processes using voting system. In details, k-NN cannot deal with the problem of assigning the most frequent class to an observed instance while each group is occupying the same quantity members. Therefore, it does not have the most common class to be selected for the most appropriate prediction class.

Fortunately, this difficult situation will not be

encountered for $K=1$ as well as for the dataset which has two types of classes. This challenging situation mainly leads k-NN to a constant drain on its accuracy over an increase in K value. To overcome this issue, this paper introduces a new approach, Regional Distance-based k-NN (RD-kNN) and to lay bare the efficiency of this propose method, we did the experimentation by utilizing three distance measurements that are Euclidean

Fig.1. k-Nearest Neighbor

distance, Cosine similarity, and Mahalanobis distance. The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes related works. Section III is about distance metric and section IV gives the new approach, RD-kNN.

Section V gives the relevant information of data sets, and section VI details the experimentation of new models on five data sets by comparing the processing time performance and the prediction accuracy of the new approach with classical k-NN. Finally, section VII is the conclusion of this paper.

II. RELATED WORKS

The k-Nearest Neighbor appeals to many researchers about its simplicity and high prediction accuracy among machine learning methods even though it is a lazy learning method. Therefore, researchers have been investigating the weak points of k-NN from a different point of views to innovate normal k-NN with the greatest accomplishment.

In [2], the author proposed a system, which extended nearest neighbor method for pattern recognition considered not only who the nearest neighbors of the test sample are, but also who considered the test sample as their nearest neighbors. By iteratively assuming all the possible class memberships of a test sample, the ENN is able to learn from the global distribution; therefore, it improved pattern reorganization performance.

In [4], the author proposed a system which is kNN model-based approach in classification for aiming at overcoming the shortcomings that are its low efficiency - being a lazy learning method prohibits it in many applications such as dynamic web mining for a large repository, and its dependency on the selection of a “good value” for K by automatically determining K values for different data. The authors of this paper constructed the model, which automatically chooses K makes classification faster.

Reference [5] presented a multithreading machine learning system for upgrading its classification process and proved the processing time performance by comparing the efficiency of kNN with Naïve Bayes. In reference [4], the authors designed a system, which investigates how to improve the lazy processing and how to upgrade the classification accuracy of k-NN by filtering the attributes, which are not strong enough correlation with other attributes.

The systems described above not only emphasized how to promote the prediction accuracy of k-NN but also how to upgrade the processing time performance. Likewise, this paper also concentrates on improving the efficiency of k-NN, but the investigated innovation is from different points of view.

III. DISTANCE METRICS

Regional distance-based k-NN and the classical k-NN are based on a distance metric, which is a vector of distance between the instances of a set. In this research, we did the experiments with three measurements.

A. Euclidean Distance

The Euclidean Distance is a measurement to find the distance between two points, as shown by Equation (1)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Euclidean}(X, Y) &= \sqrt{(X_1 - Y_1)^2 + (X_2 - Y_2)^2 + \dots + (X_n - Y_n)^2} \\ &= \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (X_i - Y_i)^2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where Euclidean(X, Y) is the distance between point X and Y.

B. Cosine Distance

The Cosine distance is a measurement of similarity between two vectors by measuring the cosine of the angle of them defined by Equation (2).

$$\text{Cosine}(X, Y) = 1 - \left(\frac{X \cdot Y}{\|X\|_2 \|Y\|_2} \right) \quad (2)$$

Where Cosine(X, Y) is the distance between two vectors, X and Y, (.) indicates vector dot product, $\|X\|$ and $\|Y\|$ are the lengths of vector X and Y respectively.

C. Mahalanobis Distance

The Mahalanobis distance measures the separation of two groups of objects. In other words, it is a measure of how much similar their shapes with each other by computing their covariance matrix. Mahalanobis distance is defined as follows:

$$\text{Mahalanobis}(X, Y) = \sqrt{(X - Y)^T C^{-1} (X - Y)} \quad (3)$$

Where Mahalanobis(X, Y) is the Mahalanobis distance between two vectors, X and Y and C is the covariance matrix. T indicates that vector should be transposed. The covariance matrix of vector X and Y can be defined as follows:

$$\text{Covariance}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})(Y_i - \bar{Y}) \quad (4)$$

Where C(X, Y) is the covariance matrix of vectors, X and Y, N is the number of instance, X_i and Y_i are the vector

of data, \bar{X} and \bar{Y} define vectors of mean values of independent variables. [6]

IV. REGIONAL DISTANCE-BASED K-NN (RD-KNN)

In this section, we will discuss our new approach (RD-kNN) and point out the differences between RD-kNN and normal k-NN. Actually, Regional distance-based k-NN is introduced to overcome the difficult situation in voting system for choosing the most common class among the nearest neighbors.

Fig. 2 illustrates the voting system operations of the k-NN algorithm where the training examples are red triangle, green rectangle, and blue circle. In this figure, plus symbol is an observed instance, which we want to classify which class type will be belonged to, red triangle or green rectangle or blue circle. Let's take K value 9 and assume it has 9 instances, where red triangles are three, blue circles are three and green rectangle three. A query point is shown by black plus symbol. 3-Nearest Neighbor algorithm classifies it as a blue circle in this figure, whereas the 9-Nearest Neighbor algorithm cannot classify it as a red triangle or blue circle or green rectangle. Now, 9-kNN is having a struggle in making a decision that group is the winner.

Fig.2. k-Nearest Neighbor

Here, we will discuss how to handle this difficulty as shown in Fig 3. In this new approach, it examines the nearest neighbor according to their average distance, but not considers their frequent numbers. According to Fig. 3, 9-Nearest Neighbor algorithm classifies the query point, plus sign, and a blue circle. The new approach selects only one group, which has the shortest distance from the query point. In this case, the members of each group have already occupied their own distance from the query point. Then, the average distance of each group is determined. After that, it measures the distance between the query point and each group, red triangle, green rectangle, and blue circle. In Fig.3, the blue circle group

is the closest one to the query point. Therefore, the 9-Nearest Neighbor algorithm examines that the query point belongs to the blue circle.

Fig.3. Regional Distance-based k-NN

Choosing the nearest neighbor according to their average distance can be defined as follows:

$$NN(X_i) = \text{Min} \left[\frac{C_1}{t_1}, \frac{C_2}{t_2}, \frac{C_3}{t_3}, \dots, \frac{C_n}{t_n} \right] \quad (5)$$

where $t < K$

The value of C can be computed by summing up the distance of each instance, which belongs to appropriate C defined as follows equation:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_1 &= d_1 + d_2 + d_3 \\ C_2 &= d_1 + d_2 + d_3 \\ C_3 &= d_1 + d_2 + d_3 \\ C_n &= d_n + d_n + d_n \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Where $NN(X_i)$ means the nearest neighbor of the i^{th} observed instance X_i , d is the distance, C_1 is the class type 1 and t_1 is the number of instances, which belong to class type C_1 closest to observed instance X_i and so on. Figure 4 illustrates the flow diagram of Regional Distance-based kNN (RD-kNN). In this figure, it measures the distance between an observed instance X_i and training examples Y . Then it collects the nearest neighbors according to K value. In this case, if K is 9, it collects 9 instances and so on. After that, it will investigate the nearest neighbor based on their average distance. The nearest neighbor will be classified as an estimated class.

Algorithm 1 explains the detail process of Regional Distance-based kNN by applying three distance measurements, Euclidean distance, Cosine similarity and Mahalanobis distance.

Fig. 4. Flow Chard Diagram of Regional Distance-based kNN

Algorithm 1 : RD-kNN algorithm

Let $X = \langle X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n \rangle$ to be training examples.

1. Given a query instance x_q to be classified.
 2. Calculate the distance between the query x_q and training example using distance measurement Equation (1) or Equation (2) or Equation (3).
 3. Investigate the nearest neighbor for K using Equation (5) and (6).
 4. Classify the nearest neighbor as an predicted class for x_q
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V. RELEVANT INFORMATION OF DATA SETS

In the noise-tolerant investigation of k-NN, dual-kNN, artificial neural network, and Bayes regression, we have measured the level of noise resistance of these algorithms on the medical diagnosis problems (breast cancer, heart stalog, Parkinson, dermatology, and thyroid) obtained from the UCI machine learning benchmark repository [7].

The breast cancer data set combines nine attributes with two class types (benign and malignant) for the purpose of predicting patients whether they are highly possibly suffering from breast cancer or not based on their cell tissues conditions. This data set is the donation of W. H. Wolberg from the University of Wisconsin Hospitals, Madison for researchers.

In the heart stalog data set, each instance is represented by thirteen attributes belonging to properly one of two class types (absence and presence).

The wine data set aims for the classification of origin of wines using chemical analysis. This data set that contains thirteen attributes and three class types was originally obtained from Forina, M. et al, Institute of Pharmaceutical and Food Analysis and Technologies, Via Brigata Salerno, 16147 Genoa, Italy.

The iris data set is donated by Michael Marshall (MARSHALL%PLU@io.arc.nasa.gov). This data set was built of four attributes belonging to one of three class types (Iris Setosa, Iris Versicolour, and Iris Virginica).

The breast tissue data set was created by JP Marques de Sá, INEB-Instituto de Engenharia Biomédica, Porto, Portugal; e-mail: jpmdesa '@' gmail.com, J Jossinet, inserm, Lyon, France. The data set originally contains nine attributes with one of properly health status (Class car(carcinoma), fad (fibro-adenoma), mas (mastopathy), gla (glandular), con (connective), adi (adipose)).

VI. EXPERIMENT AND EVALUATION

In this section, we will prove the efficiency of Regional Distance-based kNN by comparing with classical kNN with three distance measurements, Euclidean distance, Cosine similarity, and Mahalanobis distance. The prediction accuracy of RD-kNN is measured by using two approaches, Purity rule, and 4-Fold cross-validation.

A. Regional Distance-based kNN with Euclidean Distance

This section will discuss the prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and normal kNN primarily based on Euclidean distance. Table 1 and 2 shows the prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and normal k-NN for wine, iris, heart, and breast tissue and breast cancer. It can be clearly seen that RD-kNN can predict with higher prediction accuracy with 93 % than normal k-NN with 78% total average accuracy. Besides, in Tab. 1, the prediction accuracy of each K is higher than the accuracy of each K in Tab. 2.

Tab. 1. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Euclidean based RD- kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	100%	98%	94%	88%	82%	81%
Iris	100%	100%	100%	97%	97%	97%
HeartStalog	99%	96%	90%	90%	87%	86%
BreastTissue	96%	91%	87%	85%	80%	72%
BreastCancer	100%	99%	99%	98%	98%	98%
Average Accuracy	99%	97%	94%	92%	89%	87%

Tab. 2. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Euclidean based k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	70%	61%	64%	61%	61%	64%
Iris	96%	97%	97%	63%	63%	63%
HeartStalog	78%	76%	76%	84%	70%	71%
BreastTissue	86%	84%	72%	69%	74%	61%
BreastCancer	98%	98%	98%	99%	97%	97%
Average Accuracy	86%	83%	81%	75%	73%	71%

Tab. 3 and 4 demonstrate the prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and normal kNN by utilizing 4-Fold cross validation measurements. As the prediction accuracy using Purity rule described above, here again the prediction accuracy with 4-Flod cross validation for RD-kNN is higher than normal k-NN. The total average accuracy of RD-kNN is 75% and normal k-NN is 69%.

Tab. 3. 4-Fold Cross Validation Accuracy Measurement for Euclidean based RD-kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	71%	69%	67%	71%	68%	71%
Iris	98%	98%	98%	98%	98%	97%
HeartStalog	56%	48%	48%	50%	52%	53%
BreastTissue	69%	70%	65%	65%	59%	50%
BreastCancer	94%	94%	94%	93%	93%	91%
Average Accuracy	77%	76%	74%	75%	74%	73%

Tab. 4. 4-Fold Cross Validation Accuracy Measurement for Euclidean based k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	79%	79%	78%	49%	48%	48%
Iris	90%	90%	88%	42%	41%	42%
HeartStalog	68%	73%	74%	69%	68%	69%
BreastTissue	40%	44%	46%	61%	68%	54%
BreastCancer	96%	95%	94%	91%	95%	95%
Average Accuracy	74%	76%	76%	62%	64%	62%

B. Regional Distance-based kNN with Cosine Similarity

In this section, we will explore the proficiency of cosine based RD-kNN by comparing with cosine based normal kNN. According to Tab. 5 and 6, cosine similarity based RD-kNN could predict with higher accuracy, 90% than cosine similarity based normal k-NN, 79%.

Tab. 5. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Cosine Similarity based RD-kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	100%	97%	97%	92%	87%	88%
Iris	100%	99%	97%	97%	95%	95%
HeartStalog	97%	92%	87%	83%	79%	76%
BreastTissue	99%	86%	76%	69%	65%	69%
BreastCancer	99%	99%	97%	96%	94%	93%
Average Accuracy	99%	95%	91%	87%	84%	84%

Tab. 6. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Cosine based k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	93%	88%	88%	85%	85%	81%
Iris	96%	97%	97%	62%	98%	98%
HeartStalog	85%	79%	78%	43%	72%	72%
BreastTissue	63%	64%	58%	52%	48%	44%
BreastCancer	91%	94%	97%	97%	97%	97%
Average Accuracy	86%	84%	84%	68%	80%	78%

Table. 7 4-Fold Cross Validation Accuracy Measurement for Cosine based RD-kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	78%	74%	77%	76%	75%	74%
Iris	93%	93%	93%	91%	93%	94%
HeartStalog	62%	58%	58%	59%	54%	56%
BreastTissue	75%	65%	63%	58%	50%	44%
BreastCancer	87%	87%	85%	84%	83%	83%
Average Accuracy	79%	75%	75%	73%	71%	70%

Tab. 8. 4-Fold Cross Validation Accuracy Measurement for Cosine based Normal k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	75%	77%	78%	77%	75%	74%
Iris	94%	94%	93%	47%	93%	93%
HeartStalog	70%	70%	66%	39%	67%	67%
BreastTissue	56%	51%	46%	46%	45%	40%
BreastCancer	90%	94%	95%	96%	98%	98%
Average Accuracy	77%	77%	76%	61%	75%	74%

In Table VII and VIII, 4-Fold cross validation proves that RD-kNN with 74% prediction accuracy is better than kNN with 73% accuracy.

C. Regional Distance-based kNN with Mahalanobis Distance

Table IX and X shows the prediction accuracy of Mahalanobis based RD-kNN and kNN. It is obvious that RD-kNN has a higher prediction accuracy than kNN like Euclidean and Cosine based RD-kNN discussed above.

Tab. 9. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Mahalanobis based RD-kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	92%	95%	67%	61%	56%	55%
Iris	90%	73%	67%	61%	54%	53%
HeartStalog	90%	78%	75%	76%	73%	68%
BreastTissue	91%	75%	68%	62%	53%	50%
BreastCancer	81%	74%	72%	66%	61%	66%
Average Accuracy	89%	79%	70%	65%	59%	58%

Tab. 10. Purity Accuracy Measurement for Mahalanobis based Normal k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	53%	47%	54%	39%	38%	41%
Iris	61%	55%	54%	62%	56%	54%
HeartStalog	77%	73%	67%	43%	63%	63%
BreastTissue	48%	42%	33%	35%	34%	36%
BreastCancer	83%	82%	85%	85%	85%	86%
Average Accuracy	64%	60%	59%	53%	55%	56%

Table XI and XII demonstrate the measurements of prediction accuracy using 4-Fold cross-validation and also prove that Mahalanobis based RD-kNN has a better estimation accuracy than Mahalanobis based normal kNN with total average accuracy 52% and 44% respectively.

Tab. 11. 4-Fold Cross Validation Measurement for Mahalanobis based RD- kNN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	45%	39%	39%	35%	33%	32%
Iris	45%	38%	41%	46%	51%	52%
HeartStalog	52%	54%	51%	54%	52%	51%
BreastTissue	65%	60%	56%	54%	44%	41%
BreastCancer	81%	74%	72%	66%	61%	66%
Average Accuracy	58%	53%	52%	51%	48%	48%

Tab. 12. 4-Fold Cross Validation Measurement for Mahalanobis based Normal k-NN

Dataset	K_3	K_5	K_7	K_9	K_11	K_13
Wine	30%	24%	30%	26%	25%	28%
Iris	37%	32%	36%	42%	36%	32%
HeartStalog	53%	55%	54%	39%	55%	55%
BreastTissue	26%	24%	22%	22%	27%	25%
BreastCancer	79%	80%	82%	82%	83%	83%
Average Accuracy	45%	43%	45%	42%	45%	45%

Fig. 5. A summary of comparative study of prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and k-NN using Plurity measurement.

Fig. 5 shows the summary of the comparative study of prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and k-NN over k values from 1 to 13 by utilizing Euclidean distance, cosine similarity and mahalnobis distance. In this figure, the blue line represents the total average classification accuracy of RD-kNN and the yellow line graph is pure k-NN. It is obvious that the total average accuracy of RD-kNN is higher than normal k-NN in each distance measurement. The figure highlights that Euclidean distance is the most suitable distance measurement for both algorithms

Fig. 6. A summary of comparative study of prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and k-NN using 4-fold cross validation.

Fig. 6 illustrates the summary of the comparative study of classification accuracy of RD-kNN and k-NN using 4-fold cross validation over five data sets (breast cancer, breast tissue, wine, iris and heart stalog) from UCI machine learning repository. The prediction accuracy of RD-kNN and k-NN is investigated by

applying three distance measurements, as K varies between 3 and 13. It can be clearly seen that RD-kNN is more efficient than normal k-NN. In the investigation of classification accuracy, the two accuracy measurements (Purity and 4-fold cross validation) points out that RD-kNN is more efficient than normal k-NN.

D. Multithreading RD-kNN

This is the last section for measuring the performance of RD-kNN. According to the evidences discussed above, RD-kNN has a better performance than classical kNN. However, pure RD-kNN may have exactly or more the processing stages as classical kNN. As we know, kNN is a lazy learner algorithm. For this lack of speedy processing, this paper applied multithreading technique to RD-kNN aiming at to be a smart algorithm.

Tab. 13. Comparison of Processing Time Performance of Dual-kNN and Classical kNN

Dataset	Amount×No: of Instance	Processing Time (Millisecond)		
		Multithreading RD-kNN	Normal kNN	Improvement Ratio Over kNN
		Regional Distance based kNN		
Wine	56×178	219	438	200%
Iris	221×150	110	203	184%
Heart Stalog	55×271	422	1727	409%
Breast Tissue	58×122	106	257	242%
Breast Cancer	92×700	1156	2082	180%

time performance of RD-kNN with classical kNN for five real datasets. It can be clearly seen that the processing time performance of proposed approach for wine dataset did 2 times (200%) faster than the old one. For iris dataset, the proposed approach can estimate about 1.84 times faster (184%), heart with 4.09 times (409%), breast tissue with 2.42 times (242%), and breast cancer dataset with 1.80 times (180%) faster than the kNN.

Finally, we summarize the discussion of classification accuracy and upgrading processing time of

RD-kNN and normal k-NN as shown in Fig. 5 and 6, and Tab. 13 respectively. It is obvious that in every sector, RD-kNN achieves a higher performance than pure k-NN according to the remarkable achievement of RD-kNN.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this study, we propose the new classification approach called Regional Distance-based kNN (RD-kNN) aiming at improving not only the classification accuracy of k-NN but also processing time performance from different types of point of view. RD-kNN makes the classification by taking the average distance of each group into account, just not considering the most frequent numbers. That is the reason why RD-kNN is more efficient than normal k-NN. We did the experimentation of RD-kNN with three measurements, Euclidean distance, Cosine Similarity, and Mahalanobis distance. Besides, the efficiency of RD-kNN was measured by two considerations that are 4-fold cross-validation and purity rule. This experiment confirmed with the test cases and simulation carried out, the performance of RD-kNN is more effective than the kNN. The last measurement is processing time performance. As we know, k-NN is lazy learning approach as well as RD-kNN. For this weakness, we applied multithreading approach to RD-kNN. In this measurement, multithreading RD-kNN carries out the classification process with higher speed than the k-NN. For future work, we will apply RD-kNN to another dataset, such as radar data for weather forecasting, and traffic data. Besides, we keep seeking issues and weakness of k-NN as well as RD-kNN to be a smart classification algorithm.

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